

Table 1. Stability parameters (\bar{X} , \bar{b}_i , and s^2d_i) of six traits.^a TNRRI, Tamil Nadu, India. 1992-93.

	Panicles/plant			Grains/panicle			Percent fertility		
	\bar{X}	\bar{b}_i	s^2d_i	\bar{X}	\bar{b}_i	s^2d_i	\bar{X}	\bar{b}_i	s^2d_i
ADT38	10.05	1.306	0.249**	41.88	0.03	4.197	64.39	2.92	5.67*
CO 45	8.43	0.496**	0.002	54.75	1.37	7.148*	59.51	0.89	1.21
AD90072	9.08	1.106	0.485**	64.68	0.26	6.835*	66.94	1.73	0.48
Vikramarya	7.45	0.89	0.838**	44.05	1.23	5.914*	54.63	0.20	0.25
ADT40	10.46	1.27	0.126	64.23	1.73	29.27**	69.00	1.42	0.31
ADT39	9.17	0.93	0.382**	68.78	1.37	22.79**	68.07	-0.75	9.11*

	100-grain weight			Single-plant yield			Harvest index		
	\bar{X}	\bar{b}_i	s^2d_i	\bar{X}	\bar{b}_i	s^2d_i	\bar{X}	\bar{b}_i	s^2d_i
ADT38	1.97	2.67	0.0004**	7.74	0.55	0.063	0.40	0.66	0.00009
CO 45	2.34	0.40*	0.000	9.64	0.49	0.002	0.36	1.94**	0.00003
AD90072	1.97	0.61	0.0005**	10.08	1.02	0.202*	0.40	1.64	0.00004
Vikramarya	2.60	1.03	0.0000	9.14	1.03	1.690**	0.36	1.37	0.00020*
ADT40	2.25	0.49	0.000	13.29	1.76	0.645**	0.34	0.15	0.00020
ADT39	1.68	0.80	0.0000	10.42	1.15	0.387**	0.49	0.25*	0.00000

^a** and * = significant at the 1 and 5% level, respectively.

Table 2. Correlation among stability parameters (\bar{X} , \bar{b}_i , and s^2d_i).^a

	\bar{X} vs \bar{b}_i	\bar{X} vs s^2d_i	\bar{b}_i vs s^2d_i
Panicles/plant	0.717	-0.603	0.096
Grains/panicle	0.379	0.701	0.684
Percent fertility	0.256	0.371	-0.204
100-grain weight	-0.208	-0.388	0.475
Single-plant yield	0.880*	0.095	0.395
Harvest index	-0.340	-0.702	-0.224

^a* = significant at the 5% level.

ADT38 and CO 45 were adaptive and stable across all N levels for single-plant yield. Mean single-plant yield was low for ADT38 and average for CO 45. The stable yield was due to stable grains/panicle and harvest index for ADT38 and panicles/plant and 100-grain weight for CO 45. Although the mean of ADT40 was high, its yield was unstable across the N levels (Table 1).

The correlation analysis among stability parameters revealed that genotypes with a high mean for single-plant yield are responsive to high N (Table 2). There was no significant association between the stability parameters of regression coefficient \bar{b}_i and deviation from regression coefficient s^2d_i . It can be inferred that these two characters are not linked and are inherited separately. ■

Relationship of amylase activity to rice seedling growth at various greenhouse temperatures

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Amylases are key enzymes for starch catabolism during rice seed germination. Higher amylase activity in kernels should enhance seedling vigor. This is important where seedlings are raised indoors before ambient temperatures are warm enough for rice growth. Temperature needs to be controlled carefully in greenhouse nurseries so that seedlings can better resist

stress after transplanting.

Seeds of hybrids Shanyou 63 and D-you 63 and conventional varieties Lushuang 1011 and Fujiang 2 were surface-sterilized and rinsed in sterile water. Seeds were then immersed in water for 2-3 d (depending on temperature), incubated for a day, and sown in a nutrient solution at different greenhouse temperatures.

Seedling characters and amylase activity were determined at 7 d after sowing (Table 1). Total amylase activity in kernels and dry weight of seedlings were assayed daily. Seeds were separated from shoots and roots when measuring shoot dry weight. Extracted kernel enzyme solution was incubated with

Table 1. Effects of different temperatures on seedling characters.^a

Temperature (°C)	Seedling height (cm)			Dry weight (mg/plant)			Root/shoot	Total amylase activity (µg maltose/kernel per s)
	Mean	±	sd	Mean	±	sd		
20	4.84	0.03	d	4.45	0.03	d	0.635 a	84.0 c
25	7.88	0.15	c	7.82	0.05	c	0.464 cd	188.4 a
30	13.97	0.23	a	10.32	0.23	a	0.406 d	179.3 ab
35	10.02	0.52	b	8.16	0.14	bc	0.481 c	121.4 bc
40	0.79	0.01	e	0.85	0.04	e	-	45.5 c
30/20	8.50	0.12	bc	8.04	0.15	bc	0.499 c	152.0 ab
30/25	9.15	0.27	bc	9.52	0.26	ab	0.509 bc	137.0 b
35 → 20 ^b	9.64	0.21	bc	10.91	0.31	a	0.554 b	165.0 ab

^a60 plants for each sample. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bChange in temperature treatment.

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Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.

Table 2. Relationship between total amylase activity in the kernel and dry matter accumulation in the rice seedling.^a

Temperature (°C)	Power function formulas	Correlation coefficient
20	$Y = 0.181 X^{0.963}$	$\gamma_{lgylgx} = 0.986^{**}$
25	$Y = 0.192 X^{0.917}$	$\gamma_{lgylgx} = 0.989^{**}$
30	$Y = 0.185 X^{0.981}$	$\gamma_{lgylgx} = 0.989^{**}$
35	$Y = 0.180 X^{1.008}$	$\gamma_{lgylgx} = 0.978^{**}$
40	$Y = 0.274 X^{0.729}$	$\gamma_{lgygx} = 0.903^{**}$
30/20	$Y = 0.193 X^{0.914}$	$\gamma_{lgygx} = 0.913^{**}$
30/25	$Y = 0.187 X^{0.813}$	$\gamma_{lgylgx} = 0.912^{**}$
35 → 20 ^b	$Y = 0.182 X^{0.993}$	$\gamma_{lgylgx} = 0.980^{**}$

^{a**} = significant at the 1% level. ^bChange in temperature treatment.

pH 5.6 citric acid buffer and starch solution for 5 min. Amylase activity was stopped with 0.4 N NaOH. Solution maltose reacted with 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid and the reactant was measured with a spectrophotometer.

Greenhouse temperatures were maintained at constants of 20, 25, 30, 35, and 40°C, alternated between 30/25°C and 30/20°C day/night temperature, and changed from 35°C on day 1 to 20°C on day 7. All had a 12-h photoperiod.

Varieties responded differently to temperatures, but all showed similar

trends. Data in the tables are therefore only for Lushuang 1011 and Shanyou 63. Amylase activity was associated strongly with seedling growth, especially dry matter accumulation (Table 1). Both amylase activity and dry weight increased with time.

The greater the amylase activity of the kernel, the faster dry weight accumulates in seedlings. A power function, $Y = AX^B$, was used to describe the relationship (Table 2). It is clear from the functions that during the young seedling period, a higher shoot weight

can be obtained by increasing amylase activity of the kernel.

Among the constant temperature treatments, 30°C was clearly optimum for seedling growth and amylase activity (Table 1). The aim, however, was to transplant seedlings into the field. The temperature difference between greenhouse and field was too great for seedlings to adapt to the cold temperatures of early spring in southern China. The 20°C treatment was most like the ambient temperature, but seedlings were too short to transplant.

The greatest shoot dry weight, combined with high root-shoot ratio and high amylase activity, was obtained with the change in temperature treatment, which provides warmth for maximum germination and early growth. This is followed by a gradual hardening-off, which seedlings need if they are to adapt to cold temperatures. We recommend this treatment to produce vigorous seedlings that are adapted to field temperatures at transplanting. ■

Variability, heritability, correlation, path analysis, and genetic divergence studies in upland rice

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We studied the genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation, heritability, genetic advancement (GA), coefficients of correlation, path analysis, and genetic divergence of 37 promising upland rice cultivars. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design during 1992 with two replications.

Analysis of variance showed significant differences among genotypes for all characters (Table 1). Considerable range of variation was expressed for plant height, panicles/m², straw yield/m², grain yield/m², and filled grains/panicle, indicating better scope for genetic improvement in these characters. Grain yield/m² had maximum genotypic

coefficient of variation (GCV) (38.2), followed by straw yield/m² (37.6).

Estimates of heritability ranged from 45.9% for plant height to 96.2% for days to maturity. Even though days to 50% flowering (93.9%) and filled grains/panicle (85.3%) had high heritability, they had low GCV. This might be due to the variation in environmental components involved with these traits.

Expected GA ranged from 9.0% for panicle length to 73.8% for straw yield/m². Filled grains/panicle, productive tillers/m², and plant height showed high GA with high GCV and should be considered for obtaining high genetic gain.

Grain yield/m² was positively and significantly correlated with straw yield/m² ($r = 0.604$) and filled grains/panicle ($r = 0.434$), while it was negatively and significantly correlated with days to 50% flowering ($r = -0.495$) and maturity ($r = -0.405$). Plant height was significantly and positively correlated with straw yield/m² ($r = 0.714$), panicle length ($r = 0.632$) and filled grains/

panicle ($r = 0.355$), while it was significantly and negatively correlated with productive tillers/m² ($r = -0.441$).

Panicle length was significantly and positively correlated with straw yield/m² ($r = 0.547$) and filled grains/panicle ($r = 0.425$). Filled grains/panicle was significantly and positively correlated with straw yield/m² ($r = 0.647$) and grain yield/m² ($r = 0.434$).

Path analysis studies indicated filled grains/panicle extend direct positive influence on grain yield (0.077). This high magnitude of association between the two was because of the positive indirect effect through days to maturity (0.695) and productive tillers/m² (0.114).

Correlation and path analysis studies revealed that filled grains/panicle, plant height, and panicle length were important yield-contributing characters. They should be considered when adopting selection criteria in upland rice breeding programs.

Genetic divergence studies using D² analysis showed that the genotypes fall into seven distinct clusters (Table 2).